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A CASE STUDY ON E- SUGAM

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Introduction

Sugam – acronym-

Simple Uploading of Goods Arrivals and Movements.

e - Sugam is a procedure set by the Commercial Taxes Department of Karnataka State for all the dealers who are transporting the designated goods of worth over Rs.20000 to other dealers and upload the same in the department's website and obtain a unique number as proof of uploading such transporting details. The unique number thus obtained shall be produced to the check post officer on reaching a check post. Every dealer registered under Karnataka Value Added Tax 2003, needs to upload the details of notified goods being dispatched or transported, in the format available in CTD's website before the movement of goods commences. Thus a dealer/trader before dispatching goods by a truck, first uploads each transaction details onto the CTD's website electronically, obtains an acknowledgement, e-SUGAM for having uploaded and then uses this e-SUGAM as a valid document for the transportation of goods. This would ensure that all sales are properly accounted and there will not be any problem of tax evasion.¹

Advantages

The following are the benefits of e-SUGAM System:

- Increased tax revenues for the department
- Better compliance to law by dealers
- Enabling processing of information by dealers
- Better utilization of Human Resources
- Simplified procedures and avoiding frequent visits of dealers to tax offices
- Reduces detention of vehicles at check posts

¹ http://164.100.80.121/vat2/web_common/VATDownload/esugamusermanualV3.pdf

- Shifting capture of information from paper mode to electronic mode – Paperless process.²

Project e- Sugam was conceived to reduce the hardship of tax payers (dealers) on the one hand and to ensure better tax compliance by introducing self policing amongst the tax payers on the other. Under the new concept – e Sugam- **the law mandates the traders to inform the department about each transaction (bulk) before the movement of goods against the old practice of traders moving the goods first and then informing about the transactions later on –periodically.** The dealer now has to upload the details of each bulk transaction on the central server of the department. Upon uploading the system gives a unique acknowledgement number. This acknowledgement number then becomes the passport for the truck at the check post. Each dealer has to identify himself/herself through a system of username and password.³

The logic of checkpoints

- In order to ensure that all big transactions are covered by bills checkpoints were established at vantage locations.
- Logistics demand that all retails transactions are to be preceded by bulk transactions therefore the focus was on ensuring proper accounting of the bulk transactions – which necessarily have to move in trucks.
- At the checkpoints the truck would be stopped and it would be verified whether the consignments are covered by valid bills.
- A copy of the bill would be collected for a future possible verification with the dealers books of accounts.⁴

The problems at checkpoints

- Volumes are huge – 25,000 bills collected at a checkpoint per day.
- Truckers are made to wait for long hours.
- System is opaque.
- The bills collected cannot be processed
- The purpose of checking not being served
- Unauthorized persons work around checkpoints
- There are complaints of harassment⁵

² ibid

³ <http://egovreach.in/uploads/presentation/karnataka/e-sugam.pdf>

⁴ ibid

Technological Intervention

- Web based system for 400,000 dealers to access and establishes their identity on the system with username and password.
- The main servers are in NIC data centre and the backup server is in the State data centre. All the servers are inter-connected.
- The software has been developed by an in-house team of NIC.
- The checkpoints have been provided with thin clients so as to ensure trouble free services.
- The software has been integrated with SMS gateway of NIC for verification on mobile phones.
- A control room, working 24X7, staffed by CTD officers has been established. This control room assists the dealers as well as officers in troubleshooting problems relating to e-Sugam.⁶

But how do the checkpoints verify?

- Since the trucks would be carrying only the acknowledgement number, the checkpoints had to enable to pull out the details of transaction corresponding to the given number, so that the truth of the details could be verified.
- All checkpoints were connected to the central server through the CTDSWAN.
- The truck driver reporting at the checkpoint would just inform the e-sugam number (acknowledgement number) to the checkpoint officer.
- The checkpoint officer can access the system using his/her own username and password. Whenever a checkpoint officer verified a transaction his/her own name also gets captured in the computer – **thereby fixing their accountability.**⁷

Environment Building

- The project would not have been successful without the 400,000 strong dealers community accepting it.

⁵ ibid

⁶ ibid

⁷ ibid

- Representatives of the trade bodies were involved in the design of the system. Each major step in the system was vetted by the trade bodies.
- The project was presented to the dealers as a win-win situation.
- Before the launch of these services, the dealers were given the facility of on-line downloading of 'C' forms. The dealers were extremely happy with the availability of 'C' forms on demand, online and at their door steps.
- The fact that delays and harassment at checkpoint would end, was widely canvassed. It was highlighted that dealers would no longer be required to come to the tax offices every now and then.
- Print media was extensively used to spread the benefits of the initiative.
- The next important task was to train the dealers in the use of the new system.
- User manuals for dealers were developed and kept on the website.
- Training programmes were organized all over the state and these were well attended.
- Dealers/transporters were advised that they could approach any office of the department to learn or clarify any aspect of this project.
- Administrative instructions were issued that any truck having e-sugam should not be detained or penalized for technical mistakes.
- The dealers are advised periodically about the features of e-sugam and how to prevent misuse e-sugam.
- The real success came when the trade bodies started organizing training programmes themselves.⁸

Capacity Building

- All the officers and officials of the Commercial Taxes Department (CTD) had to be acquainted with the system and made capable to handle it.
- It was decided that all officers and officials should be trained in sugam/suvega and other aspects of governance. This would render the system immune to any transfers/promotion etc.
- The challenge was to train about 800 officers and about 6000 officials.
- A Training Needs Assessment exercise was conducted at the Administrative Training Institute, Mysore.

⁸ ibid

- All officers were trained at ATI Mysore. They were trained in batches of 30-35 and each batch was trained for a week.
- The Commissioner and the DG, ATI, made it a point to address each batch.
- The trainers were a mix of experts from outside and from within the department.
- Representatives of trade bodies also addressed their the officers explaining the dealers viewpoint
- Officials are being trained at 7 District Training Institutes. So far 33 batches have been trained totaling 1000 officials. These trainings are also for a period of a week.
- Nodal officers of the rank of Deputy Commissioners of Commercial Taxes have been nominated in each Division. These are officers who have better knowledge of the IT initiatives. They act as mentors for their colleagues.

Outcomes

- Dealers no longer come to the offices of Local VAT Offices (LVO) to obtain Delivery Note.
- About 15,000 visits saved per day.
- Tonnes of papers saved resulting in Going Green
- Waiting times for Transporters at Check Posts has been reduced drastically
- Zero scope for corruption
- The system has made tax administration more efficient:
 - –The local tax officer does not have to waste time on mundane activities like issuing delivery notes. His/her job has been enriched. They get more time to do analytical work.
 - –Automatic capture of voluminous data – which hitherto was impossible.
 - Checkposts became much more friendly. The delays at checkpost were reduced.
 - The drudgery of checkpost officer has reduced and his/her accountability has increased.
 - The system is very environment friendly. It saves about one ton of paper per day.⁹

Unique features

- It was totally home grown.

⁹ ibid

- The project is an excellent example of convergence amongst government agencies and convergence of resources.

–The project was pioneered by the Commercial Taxes Department, the software and technical component was provided by the NIC, data centers of the state government as well as the NIC